

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO DESIGNING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN TRAINING FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article reveals the problem of pedagogical design of the educational process. The importance of setting goals on which learning outcomes depend is also substantiated.*

Keywords: *pedagogical process, pedagogical design, learning, lesson goals, goal setting.*

Pedagogical design cannot be unambiguously attributed to the objective or subjective aspects of pedagogical activity. It is multifunctional, and its integrity is based on the idea of improving pedagogical activity, about the future image of a culturally consistent, personality-oriented educational system and the pedagogical processes corresponding to it.

Since the 90s. In the 20th century, the theory and practice of pedagogical design received widespread development. The question arises, what is pedagogical design?

Pedagogical design is the highest level of pedagogical activity, manifested in the teacher's creativity, in the constant improvement of the art of teaching, education and human development. Pedagogical creativity is considered as a state of pedagogical activity in which the creation of something fundamentally new in content, organization of the educational process, and in solving scientific and practical problems occurs.

Pedagogical design is a complex task, the solution of which is carried out taking into account the sociocultural context of the problem under consideration, and in which sociocultural, psychological, pedagogical, technical, technological and organizational and managerial aspects interact and complement each other.

An innovative approach to the design of the educational process in the preparation of future Technology teachers depends on the level of technological competence of teachers and is determined on the basis of the following main criteria:

- 1) expediency (in direction);
- 2) creativity (according to the content of the activity);
- 3) technological effectiveness (according to the level of pedagogical technology);
- 4) optimality (by choosing effective means);
- 5) productivity (by result).

The goals of pedagogical projects are only being outlined and must be adjusted as intermediate results are achieved. Once formulated, goals should not be viewed as immutable. During the implementation of an innovative project, under the influence of changes in the project environment and the resulting intermediate results, the goals of the project may undergo changes. Therefore, goal setting should be considered as a continuous dynamic process in which current situations and trends are analyzed and, if necessary, goals are adjusted.

Goals are one of the most important categories in educational technologies and in the professional training of specialists.

With the appearance of a goal, activity, independence arises, and decisions are made. It is the goal that predetermines the result, it predicts it. Under the target, i.e. Based on the predicted result, content and methods are selected that are most appropriate for the purpose and ensure the result.

In the pedagogical practice of vocational education, an approach has been established - setting goals by the teacher for students. This situation is changing radically today, and new technologies are becoming in demand. What needs to change and why?

If the goal for joint action was formed without your participation, it means that your needs are not taken into account and there is no basis for active action. If this exercise is repeated many times, it is either learned as a rule of one's own actions (not taking into account the needs, interests of another), or it causes protest, resistance, and irritation. Overcoming this stereotype is democratization in education.

To understand the role of goals in the pedagogical process, their purpose, their functions, let us imagine several different pedagogical situations that arise in classes in the higher education system.

Let us characterize the dynamics of goal formation among students:

- 1 - zero need;
- 2 - some interest appears;
- 3 - the goal is formed during the lesson;
- 4 - came with a very specific purpose (real, unreal);
- 5 - self-determined during the lesson;
- 6 - self-determined at the beginning of the lesson.

Dynamics of teacher goal formation:

- 1 - read a prepared lecture;
- 2 - set your goal for students;
- 3 - identify the interests and needs of students;
- 4 - predict the increase that students will receive when mastering the content, mastering the method,
- 5 - self-determination during the lesson;
- 6 - determine yourself at the beginning of the lesson.

The analysis carried out allows us to conclude that the function of goals is to "launch" the pedagogical process, and their absence is an "idling" action, an ineffective action, with an insignificant result.

The sources of goals are in contradictions and inconsistencies between:

- internal needs, norms and abilities in professional activities, i.e. his internal problems, conflicts;
- the needs, norms and abilities of students and teachers.

Norms for the functioning of the system, "goals": if the content is acquired through the word, methods through action, then goals through thought. They cannot be learned and passed for a test or exam based on the objectives.

Goals are formed from needs. In the process of reflection, needs are rearranged, their hierarchy changes, those that fit the answer to the question "for what?" are selected, which in

significant, dubious situations rises to the question “for what?”, “for what values?” Here preferences, morality, humanity, and level of spirituality are revealed. Thus, the formation of goals trains in managing one’s own needs, which is a process of education. The level of good manners is one of the signs of an educated, cultured person.

The goal is one of the elements of the pedagogical process and is interconnected with others: content and method. The goal determines the choice of content and the choice of method, and the structure of the content allows everyone to advance in accordance with their goal, take actions to master the content, growing their internal norms and their own abilities.

Having considered the “pedagogical process” system and its “goals” subsystem, we can continue structuring the “Goals” system. Since the pedagogical process consists of three processes: education, training, development, it makes sense to consider the elements: educational goals, learning goals, development goals and their relationships.

A goal is an ideal (in ideas) result, and a result is a realized (in real) goal. Their coincidence (or non-coincidence) depends on the chosen content and method. The relationship model below applies to both the actions of the teacher and the actions of future Technology teachers.

Pedagogical design is a mechanism for developing technology in pedagogical theory and practice.

So, taking as the main features of the project

1. Change as the main content of the project
2. Goal time limits
3. Time limits on project duration
4. Presentation of the project as a system of means to achieve the future
5. Certainty of the beginning and end of the project work.

The unity and integrity of the elements of consciousness is subject to change in educational processes. New qualitative state: needs from which goals were formed; abilities that were transformed by mastering the method in the joint activities of teachers and students; norms that have changed due to the assimilation of new information. In the educational process, there is a process of different, new self-determination of future teachers of Technology to understand their own professional activities in changed conditions (or approval of the existing one); there is a process of renormalization, search for new norms of professional activity in new conditions, obtaining new information (or taking inventory of existing information), mastering new ways of activity, improving the culture of communication, reflective culture, and technical thought.

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